

RESEARCH SUPPORT AND TRAINING OFFER FOR SOCIAL SCIENTISTS Activities of CESSDA

CESSDA's main goal is to **increase the reuse of data** in the Social Science domain.

It is part of **CESSDA's mission to facilitate teaching and learning in the social sciences**. CESSDA has a **Training Working Group** that is responsible for supporting continuous learning and training of its Service Provider staff and the social science user community.

TTT

TRAIN THE TRAINER

- . Presentations
- . Exercises
- . Documents (DMP Questions)
- . Images
- . Workshop outlines

Material prepared and workshops delivered will help you answer important questions.

DATA LIFE CYCLE

I. Plan

- . What is data management and why do you need DMP?

II. Organise and Document

- . How should you organise your data and metadata in order for it to be easy for others to find and use?

III. Process

- . Do I have the final version of my data (versioning)? Will I and others be able to use it in the future (interoperability)?

IV. Store

- . How and where will the data be stored during the project (backup, security)?

V. Protect

- . How do you comply with data protection laws (GDPR)? What about ethical duties to participants?

VI. Publish

- . Do you want to make your data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)? Do you want others to acknowledge your work and cite you?

VII. Discover

- . Did you check if data for your research already exist? Search data repositories (CESSDA Data Catalogue)! Evaluate quality!?

DATA MANAGEMENT EXPERT GUIDE

Online

- . Workshops at SSH **summer schools**
- . **National workshop** - covering national issues
- . Thematic workshops (**GDPR, sensitive data, FAIR**)
- . Conferences
- . Prepare DMP and monitor projects RDM

GUIDE

VIDEO

TRAINING

DATA DISCOVERY

- . **Webinars** (How to find data in Europe, about Ageing, Migration, Political Behaviour, Poverty)
- . **Workshops** (European Attitudes and Values, European User Conference for EU-Microdata)

EVENT CALENDAR

COMING in the future

IN COLLABORATION

- . Train the Trainer Toolkit
- . SSHOC Training Networks
- . Larger events and workshops (Data Protection, Data Stewardship, Data Science)

CESSDA

DMEG guide in PDF

Data Archiving GUIDE

Training for data users and producers

European Training Network

SSHOC

@SSHOpenCloud

@CESSDA_Data

Trust experts in CESSDA archives to make your data and documentation visible and accessible.